

the methylene blue reduction test (MBRT) provide an estimate of bacterial load, sanitary conditions, and keeping quality of milk. Elevated somatic cell count (SCC) is the most reliable indicator of subclinical mastitis and is internationally recognized as a standard for milk quality assessment (Deshapriya *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, the California mastitis test (CMT) enables identification of specific infected quarters, allowing for targeted intervention. The indiscriminate use of antibiotics without prior sensitivity testing can lead to treatment failure and the emergence of resistant bacterial strains. Antibiotic sensitivity testing (ABST) offers an evidence-based approach to identify the most effective therapeutic agents (Erskine *et al.*, 2003). This study aimed to evaluate raw milk quality, detect mastitis, and assess the antibiotic susceptibility of bacterial isolates under field conditions in Tiruchirappalli district.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted over a period of 6 months in 25 dairy farms located in Tiruchirappalli district, Tamil Nadu (India). A total of 126 milk samples were collected aseptically from 2 to 3 lactating cows per farm, including both animals exhibiting the clinical signs of mastitis and apparently healthy cows for comparison. Teat ends were cleaned and disinfected with 70% ethanol, and the first streams of milk were discarded before collecting approximately 10 mL of milk into sterile containers.

Milk quality was assessed using the MBRT and SCC. The MBRT was performed on-farm to estimate bacterial load and overall hygienic status, where milk samples were incubated with methylene blue and the time for colour reduction indicated bacterial contamination and keeping quality. SCC was measured using the Ekomilk Horizon Milk Analyzer, with elevated counts indicating subclinical mastitis. Mastitis detection was carried out using the CMT, where equal volumes of milk and bromocresol purple reagent were mixed in a four-cup paddle, gel formation indicated a positive reaction, while no change indicated negative (Johri *et al.*, 2023).

All positive samples were transported to the Veterinary University Training and Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli, for lab analysis and to guide evidence-based antibiotic therapy.

Milk samples that tested positive by MBRT, SCC, or CMT were cultured on nutrient, blood, and MacConkey agar at 37°C for 24-48 h, and bacterial isolates were identified based on colony morphology, Gram staining, and standard biochemical tests. Antibiotic sensitivity testing was performed on Muller-Hinton agar using commercially available antibiotic discs, including enrofloxacin, oxytetracycline, gentamicin, ciprofloxacin, penicillin, and cephalosporin. Zones of inhibition were measured and interpreted according to CLSI guidelines (Erskine *et al.*, 2003).

The proportion of positive samples and the antibiotic sensitivity profiles were calculated. Percentages of resistant and sensitive isolates were summarized for each antibiotic and organism. Descriptive statistics were used to interpret results and identify patterns of resistance in the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Out of 126 samples analysed, 54 (42.9 %) were positive for bacterial growth and showed elevated somatic cell counts, indicating the presence of subclinical mastitis. Similar prevalence level of subclinical mastitis has been reported by Sri Balaji and Senthilkumar (2017). The MBRT showed less time for decolourisation in mastitis milk samples indicating higher bacterial load and poor hygienic conditions during milking, in the line with findings of De Silvaa *et al.* (2016). The CMT identified the affected quarters and correlated with somatic cell counts, and confirmed earlier observations that CMT is a reliable cow-side diagnostic tool for large scale screening.

The most frequently isolated organisms in 54 positive samples for bacterial growth included *Escherichia coli* (53.70%), *Staphylococcus aureus* (31.48%) and *Streptococcus* spp. (14.82%) in contrast to the finding of Kumari *et al.* (2018) (Table 1).

Table 1: Prevalence of bacterial pathogens isolated from mastitis (n = 54)

S. No.	Isolates	Number of positive samples	In percent (%)
1.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	29	53.70
2.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	17	31.48
3.	<i>Streptococcus spp.</i>	8	14.82
Total		54	100

Antibiotic sensitivity testing of the bacterial isolates of 54 mastitis milk samples revealed that the most isolates were susceptible to aminoglycosides (94.44 %) and fluoroquinolones (85 to 88 %). However, only 39 to 42 % isolates showed sensitivity to β -lactam antibiotics indicating high resistance or the reduced efficacy of this class (Table 2). Similar resistance patterns against β -lactams in mastitis pathogens have been reported in Tamil Nadu and other parts of India, which may be attributed to frequent and indiscriminate use of these antibiotics at the farm level (Rajarajan, 2020, Arthanari Eswaran *et al.*, 2018). The sustained sensitivity to aminoglycosides and fluoroquinolones recommends that these drugs remain viable options for therapy, but earlier studies caution that over-reliance on these antibiotics may eventually lead to resistance development (Radostits *et al.*, 2007).

Table 2: Sensitivity of antibiotics towards mastitis organism based on ABST (n=54)

Type of Reaction	Classes of Antibiotics					
	Fluroquinolones		Polyketides	Aminoglycosides	β -lactam antibiotics	
	Enrofloxacin	Ciprofloxacin	Tetracycline	Gentamicin	Penicillin	Cephalosporin
Sensitivity: No. (%)	48 (88.89)	46 (85.19)	36 (66.67)	51 (94.44)	23(42.59)	21 (38.89)
Resistance: No. (%)	6 (11.11)	8 (14.81)	18 (33.33)	3 (5.56)	31(57.41)	33 (61.11)

The findings of the present study highlight the importance of evidence-based antibiotic therapy guided by regular antimicrobial susceptibility testing. Experimental treatment without laboratory support often results in poor therapeutic outcomes and endorses resistance. In agreement with previous research, effective mastitis management requires a multi-pronged

approach that includes maintaining strict udder and milking hygiene, early detection of subclinical cases using SCC and CMT (Sinha *et al.*, 2024) and sensible use of antimicrobials based on sensitivity profiles.

The study confirmed a high prevalence (43%) of subclinical mastitis in dairy cows of Tiruchirappalli district. While aminoglycosides and fluoroquinolones showed promising efficacy, reduced sensitivity to β -lactams highlights the growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance. Early detection using simple field-level tests, combined with evidence-based antibiotic therapy and improved farm hygiene, can improve milk quality, reduce economic losses, and safeguard public health. Further, it is suggested to conduct the study for a long period to assess the pattern of mastitis incidence and antibiotic sensitivity profiling.

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Conflict of Interest: None

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